

Effect of polyols on the release and on the self-diffusion coefficient of sweet aroma compounds in soda beverages

CARMEN BARBA¹, Juan Ignacio Maté¹, Alfonso Cornejo²

¹ISFOOD - Institute for Innovation & Sustainable Development in Food Chain, Public University of Navarre, Campus de Arrosadía, 31006, Pamplona, Spain, carmen.barba@unavarra.es

²INAMAT- Institute for Advanced Materials and Mathematics, Public University of Navarre, Campus de Arrosadía, 31006, Pamplona, Spain

Abstract

The overall objective of this study was to investigate the effect of polyols on the release of an aroma compound named 2-phenylethanol in solution. The first set of experiments evaluated the effect of three polyols named erythritol (MW=122.12), D-mannitol (MW=182.17) and maltitol (MW=344.31) on the concentration of 2-phenylethanol in the headspace. The headspace concentration of aroma compounds was analysed by headspace solid-phase microextraction gas chromatography (HS-SPME-GC). In the second set of experiments, self-diffusion coefficient of 2-phenylethanol was calculated in presence of polyols by diffusion ordered spectroscopy-nuclear magnetic resonance (DOSY NMR). Results showed that the structures of all polyols had a relevant effect on the headspace volatility of 2-phenylethanol. The “salting-out effect” was slightly increased with the molecular weight of the polyol. The aroma self-diffusion coefficient of 2-phenylethanol was not affected with the presence of polyols at low concentration (10%, w/w). Both methods provide complementary information on flavour-food matrix interactions, which it is critical for the selection of aroma compounds to formulate new soda beverages with polyols. This study provides a new insight about how one may combine aroma and polyols to formulate soda beverages when replacing sucrose.

Keywords: polyols, 2-phenylethanol, release, self-diffusion coefficient, HS-SPME-GC

Introduction

Polyols are molecules able to modulate sweet perception and they are used as sweeteners. Their similarities to sugars, both in sweet flavour and physical properties, have resulted in using them as low-calorie sweeteners and bulk sugar replacement. Moreover, polyols intake are not linked with obesity, diabetes and caries. The microbial production of polyols and the current regulation have been recently reviewed [1]. Due to the industrial impact that may have this sucrose alternative, its use is controversial in food industry. Polyols are used generally in combination with other high intensity sweeteners to avoid high concentrations while keeping a high sweet perception.

Flavour release during consumption is an important aspect because of its influence on flavour perception and on the acceptability of food or beverage products [2]. The study of the interactions that may occur with flavour compounds contributes to understand flavour release. Interactions of flavour compounds with other food matrix compounds such as proteins, carbohydrates and lipids have been well studied as they have a strong influence on the release of flavour compounds from foods [3, 4]. However, the literature contains only a few examples of the impact of polyols on flavour release in food and beverage products [5-8]. Another approach, much less explored in the industry and in the literature, is to reduce polyols concentration from food and beverage products using odour associated to sweet taste compounds, based on the fact that an odour may evoke a taste [9].

The aims of this work were: i) to evaluate the effect of polyols (erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol) on the headspace concentration of a flavour compound, namely 2-phenylethanol, by HS-SPME; ii) to quantify the self-diffusion coefficients of 2-phenylethanol by DOSY NMR to explore mechanism of interactions between polyols and 2-phenylethanol.

Experimental

Samples and chemicals

Erythritol (C₄H₁₀O₄, MW=122.12 g/mol), D-mannitol (C₆H₁₄O₆, MW=182.17 g/mol) and maltitol (C₁₂H₂₄O₁₁, MW=344.31 g/mol) were provided by Cargill (Minnesota, USA). The volatile compound 2-phenylethanol was provided by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Solutions of 2-phenylethanol were prepared in deionized water (reference solution) at 100 mg/L. Solutions of each polyol 10% (w/w) with 2-phenylethanol (100 mg/L) were stirred at 200 rpm for 40 minutes and sonicated for 30 minutes at room temperature (19 ± 1 °C).

HS-SPME

Although experimental conditions used for the HS-SPME procedure were initially set as suggested by other authors [10, 11] slight variations were introduced in the present work with a view to the specific requirements of the proposed objectives. Different parameters were tested to optimize this method: absorption of two fibres from the same batch, two different type of fibres (DVB/CAR/PDMS and Carboxen/PDMS) and sample volume in the vial (1, 3 and 5 mL). Finally, a Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA) holder and a SPME Stableflex 2 cm-50/30 DVB/CAR/PDMS fibre was employed to retain 2-phenylethanol. According to the recommendations of the manufacturer, prior to its use the fibre was conditioned for 60 min in the GC injector port maintained at 270 °C. Before each analysis, the fibre was cleaned at 250 °C for 5 minutes. 3 mL of each sample was placed in a 10 mL vial and sealed with parafilm. In all cases samples were placed in a bath at 25 °C for 1 h. Volatile compound was extracted at different extraction times (1, 5, 30, 60, 80, 120, 140 and 180 min). Volatile compounds were desorbed by inserting the fibre into the GC injector set at 250 °C for 5 min. HS-SPME analysis were done in triplicate RSD value were less 5%.

GC-FID analysis

An Agilent 8860 equipped with split/splitless injector and a FID detector was used. A 30 m × 0.32 mm I.D. fused silica capillary column coated with a 0.5 mm layer of polyethylene glycol (DB-Wax, Agilent) was employed. The carrier gas was He at 30 cm/s. The oven temperature was held at 40 °C for 5 min, increased to 220 °C at 5 °C/min and then held at 220 °C for 10 min. The temperature of injector and detector were 250 °C and 300 °C, respectively.

DOSY NMR

Diffusion coefficients of erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol were measured at 10 % w/w whereas 2-phenylethanol was measured at 100 mg/L in D₂O. Samples combining polyol and 2-phenylethanol were prepared at 10 % w/w and 2-phenylethanol at 100 mg/L, respectively. NMR measurements were made at 25 °C on a Bruker Ascend III spectrometer equipped with a PABBO 5 probe, at 400 MHz and 101 MHz for ¹H and ¹³C respectively and were processed using Bruker Topspin 3.2 software. NMR samples were prepared in D₂O and residual H₂O signal referenced at 4.7 ppm as reported by Savary et al. [4]. DOSY was run using *stebpgp1s* pulse program in QF acquisition mode. Diffusion delay (*d20*) in *stebpgp1s* was optimized using residual H₂O signal keeping gradient pulse length (*p30*) constant at 1000 μs, resulting in 160-170 ms. Each pseudo-2D experiment consisted on a series of 16 or 32 spectra. DOSY experiments were made in DMSO-*d*₆ at 300 K and at fixed low concentrations, 1 % w/v. The accuracy of the gradient was previously checked by the determination of the diffusion coefficient of residual DMSO in DMSO-*d*₆. DOSY analysis were processed using TOPSPIN 3.2 software from Bruker. Once F2 were phased, automatic baseline correction was run using a 5th grade polynomial function. Using the T1/T2 relaxation module installed in the module permitted FID for the first spectrum (2 % gradient) to be extracted and to perform manual integration. The integration regions were exported to the relaxation module where decay values were fitted by area using the *vargrad* preinstalled function using a 5.35 G/mm as gradient calibration constant. Graphical processing was run using 'Dynamic Center v. 2.6.1' software from Bruker. Unless otherwise stated, Stejskal-Tanner equation was fitted using the intensity obtained after the peak picking of the first spectrum corresponding to 2% gradient. DOSY NMR analyses were done in duplicate.

Results and discussion

The influence of the addition of polyols on aroma release depends on aroma compound and the type of polyol studied. HS-SPME allowed us to determine that erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol induce a greater increase in the release of 2-phenylethanol. Figure 1 shows kinetics of adsorption of 2-phenylethanol on the SPME fibre. After equilibrium time of the sample (60 min) at 25°C, SPME fibre was introduced into sample headspace and held for different times periods (1, 5, 30, 60, 80, 120, 140 and 180 min) before analysis by GC. The adsorption rate of 2-phenylethanol increases when a polyol was added. Kinetics of 2-phenylethanol in water was linear ($y = 9.62 \cdot 10^5 x + 4.70 \cdot 10^5$ $R^2 = 0.9929$) for 80 min sampling. The linear behaviour was reduced to 30 minutes sampling when erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol was added. The adsorption rate was $1.79 \cdot 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$, $1.83 \cdot 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $1.98 \cdot 10^5 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol, respectively. This result can be explained by the "salting-out effect" that polyols produce on 2-phenylethanol. Erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol are highly polar molecules that keep in the sample (water); hence, the less polar component (2-phenylethanol) is forced to be in the vapour phase (headspace). The alteration of 2-phenylethanol concentration in the headspace increases as the molecular weight of the polyol increases. This slightly difference may be due to the fact that the solubility of polyol decreases as molecular weight increases and this forces the 2-phenylethanol to the headspace. For ease of comparison, the extent of release of 2-phenylethanol in the presence of polyols was expressed in a normalized ion response related

to the response for water (100%). Changes in flavour headspace concentration with addition of erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol increase 6, 9 and 10%, respectively. This data suggests that at low polyol concentration the volatility of aroma primarily controls 2-phenylethanol release. The present study corroborates previous published results [5].

Figure 1: Kinetics of adsorption of 2-phenylethanol in H_2O (reference solution) and with: (A) erythritol; (B) D-mannitol; and (C) maltitol. Linear regression adjustment is shown in the insert of panel A), B) and C).

Figure 2 illustrates DOSY spectrum of 2-phenylethanol at 100 mg/L in D_2O (reference solution) and with erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol (10%, w/w). The DOSY spectrum of 2-phenylethanol in D_2O shows three signals corresponding to the three proton groups of the molecule, CH₂ (1) at 2.85 ppm, CH₂ (2) at 3.83 and CH (4-8) at 7.40-7.26 ppm. The diffusion coefficient of 2-phenylethanol was calculated using the integration for each of the three signals and the average of the value was $7.33 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. In the DOSY spectrum of erythritol two sets of signals to the protons of the molecule, CH₂ (2), CH (3), CH (4), CH (5) at 3.79-3.66 ppm and 3.66-3.50 ppm were used for the calculation of the diffusion coefficient. These signals were highly affected for the four $-OH$ electronegative groups of the molecule. The diffusion coefficient of erythritol was calculated with this signal and the value was $5.62 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. In the DOSY spectrum of D-mannitol three sets of signals, CH₂ (1, 6), CH (2, 5) and CH (3, 4), 3.87-3.78 ppm, 3.78-3.67 ppm and 3.66-3.58 ppm were used. The diffusion coefficient of D-mannitol was calculated with these sets of signals and the value was $4.48 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The DOSY spectrum of maltitol presented three sets of signals, 5.13-5.04 ppm, 4.00-3.72 ppm and 3.72-3.34 that were used in the calculation of the diffusion coefficient, $3.47 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. These results indicate that 2-phenylethanol, erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol diffuse more slowly as the molecular weight increases and the hydrophobicity character decreases ($\log P_{\text{erythritol}} = 1.36 > \log P_{\text{D-mannitol}} = -3.10 > \log P_{\text{maltitol}} = -4.67$).

The impact of the nature of the polyol on the 2-phenylethanol diffusion was evaluated. This was done by comparing the diffusion coefficient calculated using the integration of the signal corresponding at the aromatic hydrogen atoms of 2-phenylethanol, 7.47-7.26 ppm. The influence of the addition of polyol on aroma release presents similar effects for the three polyols studied. The diffusion coefficient was $7.33 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and slightly decreases at $5.78 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $6.44 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ with erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol, respectively. The mobility of 2-phenylethanol is not affected by the presence of polyol at low concentration (10%). Moreover, there was no difference between chemical shift of 2-phenylethanol, erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol alone and in the different media with polyols. This data suggests that there is not interaction between 2-phenylethanol and the polyols studied. These results were consistent with the indirect macroscopic information of mass transfer given by HS-SPME GC showed in Figure 1.

Figure 2: ¹H NMR DOSY spectra of 2-phenylethanol at 100 ppm (1), 2-phenylethanol with erythritol 10% (w/w) (2), erythritol 10% (3) (A); and 2-phenylethanol at 100 ppm (1), 2-phenylethanol with D-mannitol 10% (w/w) (2), D-mannitol 10% (3) (B); and 2-phenylethanol at 100 ppm (1), 2-phenylethanol with maltitol 10% (w/w) (2) and maltitol (3) (C).

Conclusion

HS-SPME-GC results show that the use of polyols causes a “salting-out effect” on 2-phenylethanol release. NMR DOSY results confirm that there is no chemical interaction between 2-phenylethanol and polyols. The diffusion coefficients were $7.33 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m²/s, $5.78 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m²/s, $6.44 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m²/s with erythritol, D-mannitol and maltitol, respectively. The mobility of 2-phenylethanol is not affected by the presence of polyol at low concentration (10%). Both methodologies (HS-SPME-GC and DOSY NMR) provide complementary information on flavour-food matrix interactions, which is critical for the selection of aroma compounds to formulate new soda beverages with polyols replacing sucrose. Other experiments will be conducted to understand how concentration and other volatile compounds are affected by the presence of polyols.

References

1. Rice T, Zannini E, Arendt E K, Coffey A. A review of polyols - biotechnological production, food applications, regulation, labeling and health effects. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. and Nutr.* 2020;60(12):2034-2051.
2. Taylor A J. Release and transport of flavors in vivo: physicochemical, physiological, and perceptual considerations. *Comp. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 2002;1(2):45-57.
3. Guichard E. Interaction of aroma compounds with food matrices. In *Flavour Development, Analysis and Perception in Food and Beverages*, Woodhead Publishing Series in Food science, technology and nutrition. 2014; 273-295.
4. Savary G, Guichard E, Doublier JL, Cayot N, Moreau C. Influence of ingredients on the self-diffusion of aroma compounds in a model fruit preparation: an nuclear magnetic resonance-diffusion-ordered spectroscopy investigation. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2006;54(3):665-671.
5. Siefarth C, Tyapkova O, Beauchamp J, Schweiggert U, Buettner A, Bader S. Influence of polyols and bulking agents on flavour release from low-viscosity solutions. *Food Chem.* 2011;129(4):1462-1468.
6. Siefarth C, Tyapkova O, Beauchamp J, Schweiggert U, Buettner A, Bader S. Mixture design approach as a tool to study in vitro flavor release and viscosity interactions in sugar-free polyol and bulking agent solutions. *Food Res. Int.* 2011; 44(10):3202-3211.
7. Raithore S, Peterson D G. Delivery of Taste and aroma components in sugar-free chewing gum: mass balance analysis. *Chemosens. Percept.* 2016;9(4):182-192.
8. Raithore S, Peterson D G. Effects of polyol type and particle size on flavor release in chewing gum. *Food Chem.* 2018; 253(1):293-299.
9. Guichard E, Barba C, Thomas-Danguin T, Tromelin A. Multivariate statistical analysis and odor-taste network to reveal odor-taste Associations. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2020;68(38):10318-10328.
10. Fabre M, Aubry V, Guichard E. Comparison of different methods: static and dynamic headspace and solid-phase microextraction for the measurement of interactions between milk proteins and flavor compounds with an application to emulsions. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2002;50(6):1497-1501.
11. Jung DM, Ebeler E. Headspace solid-phase microextraction method for the study of the volatility of selected flavor compounds. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2003;51(1):200-205.